

Study of linear and areal aspects of the upper Kundalika River Basin, Raigad, Maharashtra.

Dr. Sachin Kantilal Pise

Annasaheb Vartak College, Vasai road west, Palghar: 401202

Corresponding Author- Dr. Sachin Kantilal Pise

Introduction:

Stream Ordering:

These numbers were first developed in hydrology by Robert E. Horton (1945) and Arthur Newell Strahler (1952, 1957); in this application, they are referred to as the Strahler stream order and are used to define stream size based on a hierarchy of tributaries. Algorithmically, these numbers may be assigned by performing a depth-first search and assigning each node's number in post order. Another equivalent definition of the Strahler number of a tree is that it is the height of the largest complete binary tree that can be homeomorphically embedded into the given tree; the Strahler number of a node in a tree is similarly the height of the largest complete binary tree that can be embedded below that node.

Any node with Strahler number i must have at least two descendants with Strahler number $i - 1$, at least four descendants with Strahler number $i - 2$, etc., and at least 2^{i-1} leaf descendants. Therefore, in a tree with n nodes, the largest possible Strahler number is $\log_2 n$. However, unless the tree forms a complete binary tree its Strahler number will be less than this bound. In an n -node binary tree, chosen uniformly at random among all possible binary trees, the expected index of the root is with high probability very close to $\log_4 n$.

About Study Area: The latitudinal extent of the study area of Kundalika basin is 18°20'North to 18°35'North and longitudinal extent is 73°40'East

to 73°11'East. The Upper Kundalika maintains fairly straight course in E - W direction up to Roha and then follows as SE-NW trend.

Stream order map of Upper Kundalika river basin:

Fig no: 01

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To identify the stream ordering of the river.
- 2) To analysis the linear and areal aspects of the river

Work done carried with following points

- 1) S.O.I. Toposheet 1:500000
- 2) ARC G.I.S
- 3) Field work

Methodology;

2) Bifurcation ratio(R_b):

Strahler order	No. of streams	Bifurcation Ratio
1	345	2.42
2	142	1.6
3	86	43
4	2	2
5	1	-----

Table no: 01

The ratio of number of segments of a given order N_u to the number of segments of the higher order N_{u+1} is termed the bifurcation ratio.

$$R_b = \frac{N_u}{N_{u+1}}$$

The Rb values of study area (Table 01) indicate that there is a uniform decrease in Rb values from the first order streams to the second order streams. But an increase in the Rb values is noticeable from the third order streams. The Rb values then suddenly decrease from the fourth and fifth order. Because there are slope play very important role at NE, E, SW side of that Upper Kundalika watershed found very vast area high elevation and steep slope, these parameters control on bifurcation ratio of the present study area. These differences are depending upon the geological

and lithological development of the drainage basin (Strahler, 1964). In the study area, the higher values of Rb indicate a strong structural control in the drainage development whereas the lower values indicate that some of the area in the basin is less affected by structural disturbances (Strahler, 1964; Nag, 1998; Vittala et al., 2004 and Chopra et al., 2005). The Rb values in the study area from 2.00 to 43 indicating that the basin is largely controlled by structure (Strahler, 1957). The Average **Rb** value of the Upper Kundalika river is **9.08**.

3) Law of stream numbers : $N_i = R_b^{k-i}$

Number of Stream	Values of Law of Stream Number
1	34.29
2	4.09
3	1849
4	2

Table no: 02

The law of stream number relates to the definite relation between the orders of the basins and stream numbers. R.E.Horton's law of stream number states (1945) " that the number of stream segments of successively lower orders in a given basin tend to form a geometric series beginning with the single segment of the highest order and

increasing according to constant bifurcation ratio. The Upper Kundalika River basin has fourth order bifurcation ratio, then the number of stream segments from higher to lower orders is **34.29, 4.09, 1849, and 2** respectively which show in above table no 02.

4) Stream Length ratio (RL):

Strahler Order	No. of Streams	Length in km	Length ratio
1	345	197.42	1.94
2	142	101.59	2.00
3	86	50.55	1.69
4	2	29.86	1.28
5	1	23.27	-----

Table no: 03

Stream length ratio (RL) is the ratio of the mean length of the one order to the next order of the stream segments. This change might be attributed to variation in slope and topography, indicating the youth stage of geomorphic development in the

streams of the study area (Singh and Singh, 1997 and Vittala et al., 2004). The length ratio of the Upper Kundalika river basin is **1.94, 2.00, 1.69, 1.28** respectively which is show in table no 03.

Stream Order and Area of the Upper Kundalika river basin:

Fig no: 02

5) Morphometric data of Upper Kundalika River Gullies (2014).

Strahler Order	No. of Streams	Length in km	Cumulative mean length (m)	Basin area in sq km
1	345	197.42	197.2	263.01
2	142	101.59	298.79	44.4
3	86	50.55	349.34	15
4	2	29.86	379.2	34.33
5	1	23.27	402.47	30.73

Table no: 04

First order stream is the largest stream which length is 197.42 km and Fifth order stream is the shortest stream which length is 23.37 km. Highest stream area covered by First order stream and lowest area covered by second order stream which show in table no 04.

6) Sinuosity indices:

Sinuosity, sinuosity index, or sinuosity coefficient of a continuously derivable curve having at least one inflection point is the ratio of the curvilinear length (along the curve) and the distance (straight line) between the end points of the curve. This dimensionless quantity is obtained by the following report:

$$\frac{\text{Actual Path length}}{\text{Shortest Path length}}$$

The value ranges from 1 (case of straight line) to infinity (case of a closed loop, where the shortest path length is zero) or for an infinitely-long actual path. the conventional classes of sinuosity, SI, are:

- SI < 1.05: almost straight
- 1.05 ≤ SI < 1.25: winding
- 1.25 ≤ SI < 1.50: twisty
- 1.50 ≤ SI: meandering

In the zones of Upper Kundalika river the sinuosity index can be explained, then, as the deviations from a path defined by the direction of maximum down slope. For this reason, bedrock streams that flow directly downslope have a sinuosity index that is greater than 1. In the present study actual path length is 42.5 km and shortest path length is 32.2 km. The sinuosity index of the the Upper Kundalika river is **1.31** means this river is twisty in there conventional class.

Segments of the basin :

Sr no	Segments of the basin	Sinuosity index
1	A	1.12
2	B	1.36
3	C	1.60
4	D	1.14
5	E	1.05
6	F	1.11
7	G	1.25

Table no: 05

In the above table no 05 the data consist the Sinuosity index values of the various segments of the Upper Kundalika river basin segment A, D, F, G is 1.12 SI means this basin is windning. Segment B consist twisty drainage basin because its SI is 1.36. segment C consist meandering drainage because its SI is 1.6, and last E segment consist almost straight drainage because its SI value is 1.05.

Areal aspects of the Basin:

Areal aspects (Au) of a watershed of given order u is defined as the total area projected upon a horizontal plane contributing overland flow to the channel segment of the given order and includes all tributaries of lower order.

1) Horton's form factor (f) (1932) :

According to Horton (1932), 'form factor' may be defined as the ratio of basin area to square of the basin length. The value of form factor would always be less than 0.754 (for a perfectly circular watershed). Smaller the value of form factor, more elongated will be the watershed. The watershed with high form factors have high peak flows of shorter duration, whereas elongated watershed with low

form factor ranges from 0.42 indicating them to be elongated in shape and flow for longer duration.

$$F = \frac{A}{L^2}$$

The Upper Kundalika river basins value of (F) is **0.2755** i.e. consider as elongated type of basin shape.

2) Stoddard's (1965) ellipticity index (E) :

$$E = \frac{\Pi L^2}{4A}$$

Where E = ellipticity index

$$\Pi = 3.14$$

A = Basin area

L = Basin length

The value of E varies from 1 to 0. It is apparent from these two equations that E is inversely proportional to F. The present study of the Upper Kundalika river contains there elipticity value is **3.65**. This value is not match to Stoddard's elipticity index range.

3) Circularity Index (V.C. Miller's 1953):

Circularity ratio is the ratio between the area of watershed to the area of circle having the same

circumference as the perimeter of the watershed (Miller, 1953). The value ranges from 0.2 to 0.8, greater the value more is the circularity ratio. It is the significant ratio which indicates the stage of dissection in the study region. Its low, medium and high values are correlated with youth, mature and old stage of the cycle of the tributary watershed of the region, and the value obtained. For the present study area circularity ratio is obtained as **0.68**. $R_c = 4\pi A/P^2$ Where R_c =Circularity ratio, A = Watershed area, P = Perimeter of watershed.

4) S.A.Schumms (1956) elongation ratio (R):

According to Schumm (1965), 'elongation ratio' is defined as the ratio of diameter of a circle of the same area as the basin to the maximum basin length. Strahler states that this ratio runs between 0.6 and 1.0 over a wide variety of climatic and geologic types. The varying slopes of watershed can be classified with the help of the index of elongation ratio, i.e. circular (0.9-0.10), oval (0.8-0.9), less elongated (0.7-0.8), elongated (0.5-0.7), and more

5) Area ratio (Ra) :

Strahler Order	Area in sq km	Area ratio
1	263.01	5.92
2	44.4	2.96
3	15	0.436
4	34.33	1.11
5	30.73	-----

Table No: 06

Area ratio denotes proportion of increase of basin areas between two successive orders and can be calculated by the following equation as suggested by A.N.Strahler (1969).

$$A_u = \frac{A_u}{A^{u-1}}$$

Stream frequency (SF)

Stream order	Stream number(N)	Area in sq km(A)
1	345	263.01
2	142	44.4
3	86	15
4	2	34.33
5	1	30.73
Average ratio	576	387.5

Table no: 07

Stream frequency is the measure of number of streams per unit area. For the computation of the stream frequency, the basin conveniently divided into grid squares depending on map scale and areal coverage of the basin and the number of streams in each grid is counted, tabulated and quantified. In the present study the stream frequency is **1.48 streams/sq km²**.

$$SF = \sum \frac{N}{A}$$

$$= 576/387.5 \text{ km}^2$$

$$= 1.48 \text{ streams/km}^2$$

elongated (< 0.5). Elongation ratio is the ratio between the diameter of the circle having the same area as the watershed and maximum length of the basin (Schumm, 1956). The value obtained (drainage density) was **1.03 Km/Sq.km** for the present study. From this, it was inferred that the area is very coarser watershed. The drainage density obtained for the study area is low indicating that the area has highly resistant or highly permeable sub-soil material.

4) Lemniscate method (K) :

Chorely (1957) express the Lemniscate's value to determine the slope of the basin. In the formula $k = Lb^2 / A$. Where, Lb is the basin length (Km) and A is the area of the basin (km²). The lemniscate (k) value for the watershed is **0.90**, which shows that the Upper Kundalika watershed occupies the maximum area in its regions of inception with large number of streams of higher order.

Area ratio of the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th ,and 5th orders are 5.92, 2.96, 0.436, and 1.11 respectively. The average area ratio of the Upper Kundalika river basin is **2.08**.

Drainage density:

Drainage density is the total length of all the streams and rivers in a drainage basin divided by the total area of the drainage basin. It is a measure of how well or how poorly a watershed is drained by stream channels. It is equal to the reciprocal of the constant of channel maintenance and equal to the reciprocal of two times the length of overland flow. Drainage density depends upon both climate and physical characteristics of the drainage basin. Drainage density can affect the shape of a river's hydrograph during a rain storm. Rivers that have a high drainage density will often have a more

'flashy' hydrograph with a steep falling limb. High densities can also indicate a greater flood risk.

According to Kale and Gupta (2001) in the underlain by resistant and hard rock such as basalt, granite, gneiss, quartzite, sandstone etc. In the Upper Kundalika river basin area drainage density is very low in the streams order 1,4, and 5 and there

drainage density is 1.31, 0.058, and 0.032 respectively. Greater the drainage density and stream frequency in a basin, the runoff is faster in the study stream order no 2 and 3 having more density and there drainage density in 3.19 and 5.73 respectively.

Sr.No	Stream order	Area insq km	Number of Streams	Drainage density
1	1	263.01	345	1.31
2	2	44.4	142	3.19
3	3	15	86	5.73
4	4	34.33	2	0.058
5	5	30.73	1	0.032
Total :				2.06

Table no: 08

High drainage densities also mean a high bifurcation ratio.

$$D_d = \frac{L_k}{A_k}$$

Lk = total length of all stream segments of a basin

Ak = total area of the basin

The total calculated value of $D_d = 1.03$ which is characterized by low categories drainage density is found in the Upper Kundalika river basin.

Relief aspects :

Various relief parameters calculated for the basin are

1. Total basin relief (H) = ZH – ZL

= Height of the highest point – Height of the basin mouth

$$= 1343 \text{ m} - 6.7 \text{ m}$$

$$= 1336.3 \text{ m}$$

2. Relief ratio (R) = $\frac{H}{L_b}$

= Total basin relief – length of the basin

$$= 1336.3 \text{ m} / 42.5 \text{ km}$$

$$= 0.031 \text{ m}$$

3. Ruggedness number (RN) = $D_d \times \frac{H}{5280}$ (for one inch map)

$$= \frac{1.60 \times 1336.3}{5280}$$

$$= 0.4049$$

Analysis of the Morphometric Parameters:

Sr.No.	Name of the Morphometric Parameters (Linear aspects)	Analyses Value
1	Average bifurcation ratio	9.08
2	Law of Stream number	34.29, 4.09, 1849, 2
3	Stream length ratio (RL)	1.94, 2.00, 1.69, 1.28
4	Sinuosity Index	1.36
(Areal aspects)		
1	Horton's form factor (f) 1932	0.2145
2	Stoddert's (1969) Elipticity Index	2.84
3	Circularity Index (V.C.Miller 1953)	0.68
4	S.A.Schumms (1956) elongation ratio (R)	
5	Lemniscate Method (Ra)	0.90
6	Average Area ratio (Ra)	2.08
7	Drainage density	1.03
(Relief aspects)		
1	Total basin relief (H)	1336.3
2	Relief ratio (R)	0.031
3	Ruggedness number (RN)	0.4049

Table no: 09

Conclusion:

In the present study of Linear and areal aspects of the river basin analysis. It is a quantitative measurement and mathematical analysis of landforms. It plays a significant role in understanding the geohydrological and geostructural characteristics of a drainage basin in relation to the terrain feature and its flow patterns.

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